

REPRESENTATION OF EXPRESSIVENESS IN ADVERTISING TEXTS THROUGH PICTOGRAPHIC WRITINGS

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Abstract: This article advertising in the texts pictographic records through expressiveness and of emotionality to be expressed about considered, then advertising texts today's of the day social of our lives indispensable part the fact that and this in the texts expressiveness and of emotionality different in methods being expressed and this expression of means all the most understandable for pictographic writing that, his essence and shaped structure to describe big attention directed .

Keywords: *expressiveness, pictography, emotionality, advertising, advertising text.*

From history until today's until the day whole the world of the people marriage style, outlook, thinking, living conditions, social, political, economic potential more and more developed is going So it is this momentum with improving going our lives public information tools and publicist without texts imagination do it we can't . Everyday our activities during public information tools as well in them to advertisements we will meet face to face . Well advertising texts what And they are how tools through consumers attention to himself towards can.

Advertising text to definition giving if so , to customers known one product or the service buy get or from him to use focused, usually readers , viewers and in general consumers in memory preserved to stay for and of the population consumption to encourage service who does, in himself synthesis, precision, originality and harmony such as features embodied, title, image, slogan and short from the text Created text is the type .

Advertising in the texts above sign and features one the goal to express only when directed advertising own to the goal achieved is considered.

Advertising title

Relama picture

Figure 1. Advertising motto

Above given in the picture to advertising special has been structures reflection reached common advertising harvest did This advertising through customers how much a lot this the product buy advertising own to the goal achieved is considered.

Advertising in the texts expressed expressiveness and to pictography stopping passable if: Expressiveness (in linguistics) is language of unity semantic stylistic signs set, language of

unity contact conversation in the process of the speaker speech to the content or speech directed to the individual relatively positive or negative attitude expression tool be to get satisfies. Expressiveness of the tongue all levels for is typical. Expressiveness directly a person feeling feelings to express with depends that it was for him from emotionality separate imagination reach difficult Even some of linguists in his works expressiveness and emotionality categories one different event that interpretation " [5]

Above to expressiveness given from the definition to understand perhaps expressiveness this emotionality, impressionability means Emotionality feeling feelings through we express, feel feelings abstract face it though expressions, imo hints by means of manifestation will be Emotionality basically advertising in the texts surprise, delight, pleasure, sadness or from depression to happiness, joy transition in the style of manifestation will be done . Each in the field that it was such as advertising in the texts too in consumers advertising being done to the product relatively big passion wake up for this in advertising feeling feeling and of emotionality expression big role plays Advertising while being done directly writing , symbol and pictures main important have is counted. Humanity appear 30 thousand years ago from more times during different from symbols using they are coming First in history applied writing it is pictographic writing that called is, it is initially in Mesopotamia used Pictographic records times more developed first in coins, village economy in products tab in quality used if so, today in the day public places and public transport vehicles, bus stations, airports show for also computer in technologies sign as wide is being used . Pictographic records one sign through whole one talk or syntactic compounds express possibility , phonetics and linguistic to standards lack of justification all language layers for comprehensibility with another from the records separate because image and drawings for communicative purpose service does Piltograms two type divide by: one the idea and the meaning represents ideogram, word represents logogram is called Advertising in the texts too both of the icons type too wide applied is coming. of buyers attention attraction do, remember easy save stay, and short on occasion understand The most important thing to get is emotional emotionality good delivered can give with another from the records separate stands and that it was created long time to be despite yet still in consumption from the records the fact that attention is worthy. Advertising in the texts occurring the following icons to himself special emotionality and meaning represents

Figure 2. Income Figure 3. Discount Figure 4. Announcement .

That's it separately attention get should be x aridors always less income good quality product buy to receive they want Such products announcement to do for prepared advertising texts above discount and income sign has been currency without signs imagination to do difficult This type pictographic advertisements customers attention without pulling won't stay.

Below given advertising the text advertising poster mainly main roads to the edge is installed. Of course, in transport moving going at the time realize get easy to be for sure and short expression of means used .

Figure 5.

It is presented in Figure 5 advertising to the text attention giving if so , this in the text :

- Advertising picture
- Advertising title ;
- Advertising the source
- Phone number or electron mail
- From icons fruitful used .

Advertising being done stay place a must conditions short describe for above characters with shown icons using expressing passed . This characters through we know maybe it is stay in the place electricity energy , drink water and gas with provided about the message giving is standing.

Summary by doing in other words, advertising being done product exaggerated sent even if it is said assessment essentially right to be it is necessary Main aspects advertising texts remembering to stay easy to be need . Of this for while this in the texts skillfully used words, pictures, symbols and from the characters own in place use to know and advertising advertising being done to the product suitable has been in the audience advertising to do it is necessary Advertising texts fast, understandable, interesting and emotional way delivered in giving pictographic of records wide application that's it shows that pictographic records are universal. They are language and space does not choose, all for understandable the fact that with yet still long from years since continuous in consumption being is coming.

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